

Strategic Human Resources Management Ways to Achieve Competitive Advantage

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Abstract

Global trade, commerce, finance, production, and service sectors have expanded across continents and nations, achieving a worldwide scale. Concurrently, the proliferation of international shopping has led to a rise in individuals seeking participation in the global market, resulting in heightened competition. Current enterprises face several competitors. In this competitive landscape, the firm must distinguish itself, formulate its strategy, and articulate its vision to surpass rivals and enhance its market share. The most efficacious approaches to achieving competitive advantage in strategic management include the use of strategic human resource management techniques. The ability of firms to engage in global competition and distinguish themselves depends on the choices they make and execute in strategic human resource management. For multinational corporations, achieving competitive advantage relies on the effective management of human resources. In international corporations, human resources management is crucial for achieving competitive advantage or sustaining market share by ensuring that individuals from many cultures collaborate well, embrace the organization's values, and experience a sense of belonging.

The significance and function of human resources infrastructure in contemporary management are increasing. In organizations employing a strategic management approach, the alignment between the management and human resources departments, their shared commitment to a common objective, and their collaborative decision-making in accordance with organizational goals enhance success and confer a competitive advantage. The management divisions of firms, in establishing future objectives and goals, may cultivate a competitive edge by emphasizing their most critical asset: human resources.

Through human resources management, organizations can integrate new talents and successful candidates while maintaining a credible company image, implement ongoing training initiatives to enhance the skills of current employees, offer equitable practices, benefits, promotions, and salary increases to ensure job satisfaction, and foster commitment through activities designed to enhance employee satisfaction. Furthermore, after the termination and departure from the firm, the previous conduct and approach towards the employee or workers may be reflected in the attitude, behavior, and structure that prevents former employees from feeling alone and powerless. Furthermore, as an employer, the preference of workers escalates, resulting in a competitive advantage via the recruitment of top talent.

Keywords: *Strategic Management, Competitive Advantage, Preferability, Organizational loyalty*

INTRODUCTION

The contemporary corporate landscape has transitioned into a new industrial epoch, characterized by global integration and transformation into a worldwide framework. During the era of Industry 4.0 and the digital age, several institutions and organizations must adopt strategic methodologies and globalize to engage in international commerce and the information ecosystem, sustain their market share, and compete effectively with rivals. The impending change in strategic human resources management is leading these methodologies. Recent advancements across several domains, particularly in composition, transportation, information technology, microelectronics, marketing, and manufacturing technology, have transformed the globe into a unified market, swiftly bridging nations and fostering an interconnected economy. Advancements in high technology, information, and communication have markedly diminished logistics and communication expenses, effectively mitigating barriers that hinder cooperation and trade, such as geographical constraints that divide individuals, enterprises, nations, and commercial markets. (Aktan & Şen, 1999) The primary impact of globalization and commercial integration on international markets is the transference of competition to commercial activities and competitive domains worldwide. Companies must today contend not just with local competition inside their operational countries but also with competing enterprises in worldwide marketplaces across multiple nations. This reality compels corporations to manufacture and sell at prices lower than their competitors, necessitating an elevation of their business strategy to a worldwide scale. To achieve this objective, companies adopt a growth strategy by acquiring small enterprises that are robust in local markets but have not expanded into global markets, or by establishing business alliances with national and local firms to enhance their market dominance. Consequently, by implementing these strategic measures, they have engaged in a trend of competing with competitor firms and other global corporations in the worldwide market. (Can, 2022)

To achieve a competitive edge in global markets, distinction must be established in product, service, marketing, sales, and technical support operations, while also excelling over rivals in aspects such as financial structure and economic stability. Companies must establish a competitive strategy for their operations and organizational structures in the ever-evolving worldwide marketplaces, including all dimensions of competitiveness and excellence. (Akgeyik, 2002) The globalization of economic activity has prompted corporations to collaborate in both local and worldwide markets; conversely, it has intensified rivalry to establish superiority and differentiation among them. In local markets, regional corporations have faced competition from foreign firms seeking to expand their operations and assert market dominance. This circumstance alters the competitors' comprehension of the firms and therefore their competitive tactics. In summary, globalization has prompted the pursuit of competitive advantage and the evolution of competitive tactics. (Akdemir, 2017) In the context of a new era characterized by economic integration and globalization, companies strive to cultivate a competitive landscape and sustain it through

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strategies such as directing competitive practices, optimizing resource allocation, producing high-quality goods at minimal cost, and employing a skilled and knowledgeable workforce. (Akdemir, 2017) Institutions and enterprises must have a dynamic organizational structure that adapts swiftly and efficiently in the competitive worldwide market. Failure to adapt results in the erosion of competitive advantages, a decline in market share, and the forfeiture of sectoral supremacy, ultimately risking significant lag behind rivals within a few years. In the context of a globalized business environment, where diverse goods and services are readily available, enterprises forfeit the benefits of sourcing inexpensive raw materials, securing financial resources, acquiring affordable labor and energy, proximity to markets, managing logistics and supply chains, and accessing information. Raw resources, semi-finished goods, and technology that were formerly monopolized or restricted to a particular nation or organization are now readily available for purchase and trade in global marketplaces. The finance industry, interconnected with the globalized globe, provides financial services tailored to the specific environments of nations and organizations.

Global financial institutions established by multinational corporations seek to eradicate polarization and divides globally, facilitating the unrestricted flow of international cash. To this end, particularly capital provides lending and borrowing options to firms operating in the global market under favorable circumstances to acquire new clients. Consequently, firms with a robust framework and institutionalization may fulfill their capital, credit, and liquidity requirements almost uniformly. The elimination of trade barriers between nations and the desire of each nation to engage in commerce with others has been facilitated by the measures implemented and the legal frameworks established in this context. Currently, any enterprise in the global marketplace may get the desired commodities, services, products, and information. Advancements in intercontinental transportation and logistics have elevated contemporary commerce to significant heights, particularly via maritime and aerial transport, enabling the secure delivery of various commercial services to designated countries or regions. This equalizes firms regarding product, service, and information provision.

Numerous multinational corporations have resorted to inexpensive labor and energy to minimize their manufacturing expenses. To do this, they relocate their workplaces or factories from their operating country to areas or nations that provide inexpensive labor and tax benefits. Certain national corporations maintain parity with their rivals regarding pricing advantage by engaging local firms for contract production. Currently, numerous technology firms manufacture on a contractual basis or under their own brands in nations with low labor costs, such as China. Most textile companies operate in countries like Indonesia, where raw materials are plentiful and labor is inexpensive. Additionally, many software companies procure services from technological firms in countries such as India and Pakistan. In this century, fossil fuels and oil, mostly used for energy production, are accessible to all nations without any embargoes. Countries like China, the United States, and the United Kingdom invest in

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nations rich in oil and natural gas reserves, establish drilling platforms, process and refine the extracted resources in these areas, and distribute these fossil fuels to their own nations or globally through their established distribution networks. Currently, several oil drilling platforms exist in international seas. Fossil fuels extracted from these platforms fulfill the energy requirements of global commerce networks. Countries and organizations far from oil and fossil resources may readily get energy from sun, wind, and biofuel, facilitated by advancing technology. Companies that previously possessed financial capital, a labor force, raw materials, energy resources, information technologies, and logistical trade advantages are progressively losing these benefits due to globalization and trade integration, resulting in challenges in competing with other firms.

In the context of digitalization and globalization of institutions and organizations, the "Human Resources Management" approach has emerged as a dominant paradigm. This approach seeks to enhance work and product quality, boost employee productivity, foster job and workplace satisfaction, minimize operational costs, and facilitate employee participation in organizational processes under improved conditions, while emphasizing the human element (Bayraktaroğlu & Atay, 2016). The notion of global citizenship has facilitated the evolution of human labor and knowledge, enabling generations to collaborate and generate insights across borders and continents. Strategic human resources management is facilitating the establishment of multinational corporations that aim to enhance competitiveness in technology, information, and production sectors. This is achieved by sourcing qualified labor through brain drain from underdeveloped nations, while employees exhibit a growing willingness to work in diverse countries and regions, aided by advancements in communication technology that mitigate language barriers.

In the information and communication technology software business, organizations may generate the necessary information and software by electronically connecting with personnel residing in several locations. These digital items may be disseminated globally via the internet and other methods of information transmission. An illustrative example might elucidate this problem. The digital gaming industry, which started in the early 1980s, initially used magnetic tapes (cassettes or diskettes) for distribution. It was transmitted and exchanged globally using these magnetic cassettes. In the 1990s, the advent of compact disc technology made digital games more accessible and widely used throughout many areas. Following the 2000s and the rapid proliferation of the internet, these digital items were available for purchase online and could be installed on gaming platforms without the need of a physical medium. Today, it is feasible to access and use this digital goods from any location globally over the internet, without the need of physical ownership, due to virtual drives or extensive data storage solutions. Currently, this segment of the gaming industry has a trade volume of 100 billion dollars. (Akçetin, Çelik, Yaldir, & Herand, 2017). Game creators globally may engage in the digital gaming industry and contribute from their own nations. Numerous gaming firms have eliminated physical offices, opting instead to employ individuals globally who work from their

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homes or other locations while providing services. This exemplifies universalization, global economic output, and the notion of the workplace encompassing the whole globe. Advancements in communication technology enable companies to operate remotely from their markets, thereby gaining a competitive edge by hiring local personnel while existing in a virtual realm, offering services globally or sourcing services from independent contractors worldwide. The HR system is characterized as “a collection of distinct yet interconnected activities, functions, and processes designed to attract, develop, and retain (or eliminate) a company's human resources.” Many concur that HR is the most efficacious instrument in fostering human capital, which subsequently enhances organizational performance and competitive advantage. The strategic management of human resources offers a comprehensive view on addressing essential personnel-related challenges and success factors, as well as the formulation of various strategic decisions, which significantly influence the organization’s conduct and success over the long term. The primary aim of strategic human resource management is to develop strategic capabilities by ensuring the firm has highly qualified, dedicated, and motivated workers essential for attaining and maintaining competitive advantage. (Das Gupta, 2020)

The human-centered management strategy and sector growth guide firms towards competitive strategies that emphasize the significance of the human element in the context of globalization. This transformation has heightened the significance of human factors, a production element, in relation to competitive advantage over other production variables. Businesses that attain competitive advantage perceive and assess human resources in a manner that transcends conventional competitive advantage attributes, modify their production and management paradigms, and implement a "strategic approach" in both organizational and human resource management domains. The growing strategic significance of human resources is not an unintentional outcome. Conversely, it is a consequence of deliberate and targeted competitive alterations. (Akdemir, 2017) Contemporary enterprises with significant competitive challenges must enhance their effectiveness and efficiency in globalization and international commerce. Alongside variables like as technical innovation, capital sufficiency, cost efficiency, enhanced quality, and the exploitation of new markets as competitive advantages in the global arena, companies also seek to use the intellectual contributions of their personnel specifically. (Akgeyik, 2002) Nearly every region and nation contributes to the global commerce culture. Trade and industry, once dominated by certain nations, have recently attained a global character. Historically, Germany had significant influence in the chemical and pharmaceutical industries; however, Thailand and Brazil now demonstrate comparable production quality. Although Japan leads in electronics, high-quality technology items from South Korea are now accessible in global markets. Historically, vehicle manufacturing facilities were situated in Europe and North America. Currently, Turkey, India, Brazil, and South Korea generate sufficient production for their respective continents or regions. Historically, maritime trade and air logistics were dominated by nations like England and the Netherlands; however,

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contemporary leaders such as Qatar, Arabia, and the United Arab Emirates, established in the 20th century and lacking extensive trade histories, now excel and compete with countries possessing longstanding logistics traditions. To achieve a competitive edge, these enterprises that provide worldwide products and services employ individuals from other countries and give opportunities to people of almost every culture and ethnicity globally. In the contemporary landscape, enterprises engaged in global human resources management must source personnel from a broader and more diverse labor market (Acar, 2000).

AIM

This study aims to identify the necessary adjustments, strategies, methodologies, and actions required in human resources to attain sustained competitive advantage in strategic business management and to offer these findings to the scientific and business communities.

To achieve a competitive edge in Strategic Human Resources Management, it is essential to concentrate on three domains. The objectives are: To enhance the quality of information, products, and services created or supplied, To minimize production costs in the realm of information goods and services, To distinguish and give a superior transformation in the domain of information delivered, services rendered, and commodities produced. The paramount power that firms now or will possess for implementation and assurance across all three domains is human resources and its strategic management. Organizations excelling in these strategic domains may get competitive advantage and ensure their continuation and sustainability in future eras. Consequently, these enterprises get a competitive edge.

Improving Quality

Utilizing superior raw ingredients and guaranteeing the product's excellent quality: As previously said, the availability of high-quality raw materials is currently a resource accessible to almost all organizations. Every corporation may procure and provide logistics for various sorts of raw materials based on its financial resources. The quality of the product is influenced by the manufacturing methods, the caliber of the equipment and machinery used, and the expertise, talents, and commitment of the personnel involved in production. In the service industry, the quality of service provided is assessed on par with human labor. To achieve the necessary quality of service, information, and commodities, a business organization of competent personnel and skilled labor should be developed. Human resources departments must recruit the most qualified workforce and provide continual training

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to enhance the knowledge and skill levels of present personnel. To enhance quality and achieve a competitive edge, recruiting and retaining the most qualified people will be a strategic strategy. Collaborating with proficient individuals and integrating new workers who possess expertise can enhance motivation among present staff and elevate the level of service and information provided.

Reducing Production Costs.

The primary expense in the development of a product, products, service, and information is labor. In manufacturing enterprises, this cost approximates 30%, but it escalates to 50-60% within the information and service industries. Indeed, particularly within the technology and communication industries, a significant portion of the expenses is attributed to labor and human resources. Currently, almost every firm manufactures products with comparable techniques and methodologies. The expenditure on labor and labor losses incurred by current manufacturing procedures directly influence the product's pricing. The reduction of labor and product losses is directly contingent upon the workers' productivity and skillset. When a defective or erroneous product is manufactured, raw materials, equipment, and procedures may be promptly rectified for subsequent production. Nonetheless, challenging and rigorous human resources training programs must be instituted to enhance labor capacity and quality of work. To enhance employee productivity, one may either integrate new, high-quality personnel into the firm or augment the capabilities of current workers. The recruitment of new personnel impedes job productivity and may escalate into a significant issue if the selection procedure is flawed. Enhancing the performance of existing personnel may alone be accomplished via training. Workplace or independent training incurs expenses in terms of time, labor, and financial resources. Furthermore, employee absenteeism is unavoidable during job training. In enterprises characterized by high-quality performance, losses in product, labor, time, and materials will diminish, hence lowering production costs and enhancing efficiency. This efficiency confers cost leadership to enterprises. Organizations will establish a competitive edge by manufacturing their goods at reduced costs.

To be able to provide different or superior services, goods and information.

The differentiation approach involves distinguishing a company's goods and services from those of competitors by highlighting unique traits and presenting them in a favorable light. The primary influence in generating new product information and services, as well as enhancing current products and expertise, relies on the research and development units available to firms. To create novel and distinct goods or to differentiate their current offerings,

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firms establish research and development (R&D) divisions or engage services from organizations specializing in this domain. The development of a new product or the differentiation of an existing one mostly relies on human resources. Diverse cognitive perspectives are mostly used in research and development organizations. The most challenging aspect of strategic human resources management is identifying and assessing suitable individuals. Strategic human resources management include identifying skilled individuals, integrating them into the organizational framework, and ensuring the continuation of their employment. The commercial success of most corporations and nations is closely correlated with the funding allocated to research and development departments. Currently, R&D expenditures are recognized as a measure of the importance that nations assign to innovation and variety, and are often used as an indication of the innovation, technical advancement, and scientific capabilities of national economies. High-tech exports, akin to the emphasis placed on R&D, are seen as indicators of a nation's developmental status and indicate its competitive capacity and technical advancement relative to other nations. (Yaman, Çetin, & Dulupçu, 2020)

The emphasis placed on research and development differs by nation and location. In 2016, the entire allocation for R&D in OECD member nations amounted to \$1,149.187 million, while in European Union (EU) members, it was \$350.297 million. In the OECD total, R&D expenditures for university research amounted to \$226.66 million, with the highest allocations from the USA (\$67.52 million), Germany (\$21.66 million), and Japan (\$20.773 million), respectively. (OECD, 2018) For competitive strategies to succeed, human resources strategies must identify and exhibit the foundational elements of specific and essential demands. Currently, the key approach for achieving competitive strategy success is the identification of optimal human resource management methods. Strategic Human Resources Management is a comprehensive endeavor that examines extensive data and should be integrated into all corporate operations and management practices. Strategic Human Resources should function as a collaborator and employee alongside the senior management or boards of directors inside the corporation, as well as with managers and workers across all organizational tiers. The strategic human resources unit must possess a flexible structure, monitor internal and external advancements within the organization's operational domain, and be informed about trends in human resources management. It necessitates comprehending and assessing the beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors of workers inside the firm and aligning the company's personnel policy appropriately.

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Figure: 1 Human Resources Management Process According to Competition Strategy (Düzgün & Çetin, 2017)

(This graphic is in native language and English explanations are included in the text.)

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The optimal human resources practices for strategic management include four commonly implemented functions: personnel selection, training, assessment and remuneration, and termination, which serve as ways for achieving competitive advantage. In strategic human resources management, the employer's attitude towards former employees is crucial for distinguishing between resignations and dismissals. As the globe has transformed into a worldwide network, communication among individuals has gotten exceedingly facile. New workers might acquire the unfavorable perceptions and opinions of previous employees of their workplace or business via various social media platforms, which significantly influences their preferences for employment or firm selection. Every enterprise seeking to secure a competitive edge in the global marketplace and ensure its longevity must formulate strategic plans and implement activities that provide a competitive advantage. Companies who use the ideas of Strategic Human Resources Management will gain a competitive edge. Consequently, Strategic HRM practices are seen as a significant competitive advantage. (Akdemir, 2017)

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Strategic human resource management must concentrate on four domains to provide a competitive advantage.

These regions:

- Workplace preferability and recruitment phase,
- Employee management and evaluation
- Workplace trainings
- It is a policy of dismissal and separation from work.

To enhance its appeal to employees both internationally and domestically, bolster organizational commitment and work efficiency among current staff, and gain recognition from former employees, a company can establish a competitive advantage in human resources management by implementing strategic initiatives in these four domains. The procedures and directions to be undertaken in these four domains are delineated as follows.

Applications in Recruitment Processes and Methods to Increase Preference:

All corporate organizations undertake recruiting procedures and conduct interviews for new recruits often throughout their operations. The historical recruiting method included informing candidates via local advertising or announcements, conducting in-person meetings with interested applicants, and facilitating interviews and subsequent recruitment phases. Certain firms continuously accepted job applications and recruited new employees by choosing from previously submitted applications based on available or required vacancies. Employees with varying degrees of knowledge, skills, and education were recruited by responding to job adverts published in the media or by applying directly to local employers. During this time, both employment opportunities and personnel may be sourced from local and restricted resources. This strategy made it very difficult to identify brilliant and competent individuals, as well as to choose a suitable company and a conducive working atmosphere. The concentration of corporate enterprises in established industrial and commercial zones has led to socio-economic issues due to the recruitment of workforce from impoverished areas. To get favorable employment, those previously employed were required to relocate to metropolitan areas and sustain their lifestyles there. To get employment in multinational firms, skilled and educated individuals were leaving their home countries and relocating to more developed nations with comprehensive work infrastructures, resulting in a brain drain in their countries of origin. (Yentür, 2023)

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In the current digital and communication age, both businesses and individuals may publicly publish job vacancies and applications on online job and career platforms, therefore accessing a far broader pool of opportunities than in the past. In light of this change, firms are devising several strategic approaches to identify and recruit the most brilliant individuals. This include talent acquisition for existing workers, career fairs for prospective applicants, internal promotions, employer evaluations on career platforms, and other certifications and accolades that attest to the workplace's quality. Specifically, obtaining the “Great Place To Work®” Certificate enhances employee preference, elevating it to the greatest level globally. When individuals envision an exemplary workplace, they often see an organization with substantial perks, engaging in-office activities, and exceptional ancillary advantages. While these qualities are prevalent in many distinguished firms, the concept of an exemplary workplace for the finest establishments extends well beyond the benefits it provides. A commendable workplace is characterized by the degree of confidence workers have in their leaders, the pride they get from their job, and the enjoyment they experience with their colleagues. (Anonymous, Definition of an Exemplary Workplace, 2024) Although sustaining trust, pride, and team spirit is far more challenging than just instituting a range of advantages provided by firms, it remains an attainable objective for any company committed to fostering these elements. The Great Place to Work® Certification™ assists organizations in attracting and retaining premier talent, enhancing productivity and reputation, and acquiring significant data-driven insights into workplace culture via employee feedback. This data provides firms with critical insights into employee experiences and establishes standards for global working conditions. (Anonymous, 2024)

Organizations possessing this globally recognized credential, attainable via a wholly independent assessment procedure, both recruit and favor skilled and talented applicants while also enabling the objective measurement of work satisfaction among their present employees. Organizations with this accreditation enhance their desirability by establishing a significant distinction from rivals in strategic human resource management. The respect and consideration shown by reputable corporations towards employees invited for in-person and virtual interviews enhances the firms' corporate values. The human resources department compensates each applicant invited for a job interview for the interview duration. Even if a position remains unfilled, the applicant typically expends time and effort equivalent to one day's wage, incurs round-trip transportation costs for in-person interviews, and may receive minor promotional gifts that introduce the company to each employee involved in the interview process. Organizations that implement a human resources selection process in this manner get praise and favorable sentiments from all applicants, regardless of the outcome. The first impression of each employee participating in this interview is optimized to be favorable. Employees often choose organizations that exhibit considerate and ethical conduct and recognize the significance attributed to them.

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Executive search is another strategy used by commercial firms that adopt strategic human resource management to hire personnel. A specialized recruitment technique, commonly referred to as headhunting, wherein organizations compensate for the identification and acquisition of exceptionally qualified candidates for senior and executive roles in both public and private sectors, as well as not-for-profit entities (e.g., President, Vice President, CEO, and non-executive directors). Executive search, or headhunting, is a technique for discovering and recruiting highly specialized or skilled roles, such as senior data analysts or computer programmers, in firms facing intense competition for top talent in the job market. The approach often entails enlisting a third-party entity, usually an executive search company, but it may also include an independent consultant or advisory firm, to investigate the pool of appropriately qualified individuals with experience in competing or analogous firms or organizations. Upon generating a shortlist of potential candidates that align with the client's requirements, the executive search agency may serve as a mediator to reach out to these people and ascertain their interest in transitioning to a new job. The executive search company may conduct preliminary applicant screening, negotiate remuneration and benefits, and draft an employment contract. (Wikipedia, 2024) In some markets, there is a trend towards headhunting for subordinate roles due to a scarcity of applicants, especially for jobs under the executive tier. (Wikipedia, 2024)

Employee Management and Evaluation

Employee management and assessment constitute the paramount area of study within human resources management. Currently, it is getting more challenging to locate skilled personnel. Locating experienced individuals is particularly challenging, and the recruitment of talented workers has become a competitive factor among organizations. As capitalism and its value judgments proliferate globally, companies employ various strategies to recruit experienced and qualified personnel, often neglecting ethical standards and business ethics, in order to gain a competitive advantage by assimilating talent from other organizations. The predominant approach in this context is elevated salaries and supplementary perks. A competent and skilled individual is often less inclined to alter their existing employment situation. This metaphor may be elucidated via organizational commitment, the adaptation to a new job and environment, and theories of uncertainty. Örtenblad, Trehan, & Putnam, 2016 When an individual perceives a lack of value and believes their contributions and expertise are inadequately recognized, they may want to change their workplace and resign from their position. In highly competitive areas, competent and experienced personnel might be swiftly recruited by other organizations. These personnel begin with superior salaries and benefits compared to their previous employer. To retain existing employees and prevent the attrition of skilled personnel to competitors, organizations must implement standardized workforce measurement and evaluation methodologies in strategic human resource management. This approach will enable them to accurately discern

employee needs and aspirations, enhance feelings of significance and worth, bolster organizational commitment, and identify high-potential talent.

The primary workforce assessment and evaluation methodologies are 360-Degree Feedback and Balanced Scorecard (Purdy & Coelho, 2003). A 360-degree evaluation, or multiple rater feedback evaluation, is a method and instrument used to provide workers with extensive performance and productivity feedback derived from their self-assessments and the assessments of others in their vicinity. These may include their bosses or superiors, peers or coworkers, and subordinates. Occasionally, consumer input may also be considered. This assessment procedure is used for developmental and performance appraisal objectives, designed to enhance workers' job abilities and behaviors for improved performance and productivity. (Guevara, 2024)

Business organizations with 360 degree evaluation system;

Enhances self-awareness — A 360-degree evaluation enables workers to thoroughly examine their strengths and flaws. This pertains not just to their self-assessment but also to the evaluations by their peers and supervisors.

- Enhances morale — Employees exhibit increased motivation when they recognize their strengths and the impact of their contributions on the business.

Fosters a culture of transparency and responsibility. When individuals are empowered to provide feedback, they exhibit more willingness to assist others in achieving success and enhance their own competencies.

Decreases staff attrition – The 360-degree assessment approach facilitates the identification of workers who are unsatisfied with their positions, aiming to anticipate potential turnover events and implement strategic interventions in these areas. Offering workers ongoing input about their personal and professional development is a strategic approach to enhance their feeling of empowerment, facilitating both short- and long-term growth planning.

- Promotes ongoing enhancement – A 360-degree evaluation serves as a mechanism to identify opportunities for improvement, allowing incremental modifications to processes that are likely to influence the long-term performance of a business.

When adopting the 360-degree staff assessment approach, it is essential to clearly define its purpose and objectives and communicate them to all stakeholders. If the objective of this approach is not clearly communicated, personnel involved in the assessment process may express grievances against the shortcomings of their colleagues, clients, or supervisors, or they may perceive that they are engaging in sycophancy to enhance their own image. This personnel evaluation system considers the objective perspectives of all employees and stakeholders rather than the

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opinions of an individual, making it a tool employed by professional business organizations and workplaces that practice strategic human resource management.

Workplace Trainings

Swift advancements in social, economic, and technical domains influence workplaces and institutional settings in the competitive corporate landscape. As time progresses, new information is generated, but some professional specialties become obsolete. Employees at every level must refresh their knowledge and skills relevant to their roles. Individuals, companies, and countries must not persist in disregarding this understanding and transformation. Societies that fail to adapt to change cannot endure in a competitive landscape. There exists a danger for an abrupt loss of confidence about the newest technological advancements. Societies, businesses, and countries may achieve sustainable organization and a robust corporate culture by embracing this shift. Education is the most effective strategy for them to acclimate to this swiftly evolving competitive landscape.

Human resources constitute the paramount element influencing a company's performance. Competent and proficient staff enhance a company's performance relative to its rivals. Regardless of the diligence shown by organizations in selecting new workers, they encounter challenges related to employees' adaptability to their roles. Poor job analysis, ineffective recruiting processes, employing individuals based on personal attributes rather than credentials, and erroneous hiring choices may all contribute to these issues. Nonetheless, rapid advancements and alterations in the environment, technical advances, and the need to adapt to evolving situations may render personnel insufficient and lead to their departure from organizations. In the current information era, job prospects, working circumstances, and methodologies are evolving swiftly. To sustain competitiveness, organizations must monitor and respond to global trends. To facilitate this adaption, personnel must periodically undergo training. The significance of human resources is becoming paramount in the era of digitization and change. In the current era, there is a significant demand for employees who, beyond possessing professional expertise, can recognize their emotions and abilities, embrace innovations through self-awareness of their skills and competencies, and effectively manage their aspirations, objectives, and achievements in their work. Employees who prioritize the desires, needs, and challenges of their colleagues within the organization, possess strong communication skills through empathy, exhibit high persuasion abilities, foster a collaborative culture, embrace team spirit, and have developed skills in conflict resolution and compromise are essential for human resources management and competitive advantage. Consequently, ongoing employee and workplace training, together with structured participation in necessary training areas, has become essential for both individual employee growth and the

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enhancement of staff awareness and educational attainment. Employees in both the commercial and governmental sectors may enhance their productivity and stay abreast of technology advancements via self-improvement. (Yazıcı & Gündüz, 2011)

Individuals may enhance their knowledge and abilities, remain current with technology, pursue professions, and progress in their professional domains; these are the primary justifications for the need of business program training. Therefore, training must continue both before to and during service. The objectives of training are to enhance productivity, motivate workers, attain steady growth targets, mitigate workplace and environmental issues, rejuvenate the workplace, improve efficiency, and decrease burden. Organizations depend on the efficacy of their personnel to achieve success and attain a competitive edge.

employees may enhance their workplace performance by pursuing personal development and acquiring new knowledge. Well-designed training programs help align workers' attitudes and behaviors with the company's objectives. Consequently, staff training and development are crucial for all organizations, particularly those implementing strategic human resource management to achieve competitive advantage. Currently, the significance of human capital inside organizations is widely acknowledged, and investments in human resources are seen as the most important asset.

Dismissal and Termination Policy

In corporate companies, competent workers may sometimes be terminated owing to downsizing or market deficiencies, or employees may depart due to economic, cultural, political, and social changes. Both layoffs and resignations may result in a depletion of human capital for organizations. The exodus of skilled and essential personnel may result in the organization's proprietary information being transferred to a competing firm. Disgruntled former employees seeking retribution may divulge proprietary information and technologies to competitors, therefore undermining the company's competitive edge. To avert these issues and to re-engage individuals who were compelled to resign in the future, firms might apply several strategies and techniques. Honda, the automotive behemoth and technological enterprise with a dominant competitive edge in Japan and globally, resolved to shutter its vehicle manufacturing facilities in England and Turkey in 2021. The decision to shutter these plants, employing thousands, has likely caused significant discontent among workers and suppliers. Nevertheless, Honda has undertaken many measures to transform this predicament, which is detrimental to employees, into a benefit for the company and its reputation. The management of the Honda vehicle plant in İzmit prepared a goodbye gathering for workers. The event included memento photographs with staff and management,

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an assortment of food and beverage offerings, music, discussions, and enjoyable interactions. Honda said farewell to its workers in a manner reflective of its brand values, demonstrating caring and fostering a sense of worth among them. On September 30, 2021, Honda Turkey credited the severance compensation of all its workers to their accounts while maintaining its commercial operations in the nation. The corporation provided eight salaries as notice pay for terminating their workers. Furthermore, it awarded all staff with Republic gold coins, which serve as both a memento and a tangible asset, coinciding with its cessation of industrial operations in Turkey. Souvenir boxes specifically crafted for this departure included gifts of Nu gold. All workers without any reports or absence received a performance bonus equivalent to their most recent wage. Honda announced it would provide closing compensation to all employees, termed "crazy closing," prior to the closure. Additionally, it declared a bonus of 40 salaries for employees with 10 years of service and 48 salaries for those who have worked at the factory for over 10 years. Some workers got a fraction of the 48-salary ending pay in installments over the preceding two years, while others received their full entitlements and incentives before to the closing day. (Capital, 2021) Honda, which similarly did not abandon its laid-off employees, offered various forms of assistance to assist its former workers in achieving success in their new endeavors, so enhancing brand value and employee happiness. These measures included offering investment advice services about the use of their remuneration, giving career consultancy services to assist in job placement, and engaging talented and highly educated personnel in other firm facilities. The acts of a multinational brand such as Honda garnered the admiration and respect of both past and current workers. This incident heightened the global liking for the Honda corporation among workers. All skilled, clever, and promising individuals want to work for this firm, and the organizational commitment of present workers is at its peak. This proactive human resources management and initiative were recognized by all of Honda's rivals, inciting the aspiration of individuals from other firms to join this organization. Similar to the aforementioned Honda example, strategic measures implemented during termination enhance corporate valuation and provide a competitive edge. The qualified and knowledgeable workforce, lost due to adverse circumstances, feels a sense of responsibility for safeguarding company secrets and information technology. Consequently, these employees are more inclined to return to their previous employers upon re-employment. Thus, corporations retain their technical expertise from competitors and incentivize former workers to rejoin the workforce. Companies that use Strategic Human Resources Management to achieve competitive advantage may enhance their preference over rivals by investing in the strategies, methodologies, and practices outlined in this research, therefore maximizing organizational commitment and employee happiness. Investments in human resources represent a strategic business viewpoint that is more quantifiable than other resources and is seen highly valued and significant owing to its contributions and benefits to long-term socio-economic development.

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Publication Ethics of CURRENT SCIENCE.....Journal; It is a nationally based scientific journal that aims to ensure that scientific research and publications are carried out in accordance with basic principles such as honesty, openness, objectivity, respect for the findings and creations of others and works to realize this, aiming for these principles in the field of Health Sciences. Helsinki Declaration criteria have been taken into consideration.

RESOURCES

- Acar, AC (2000). Recruitment and Selection of Human Resources. Istanbul University Faculty of Business Administration Publications, (pp. 28-32).
- Akçetin, E., Çelik, U., Yaldir, A., & Herand, D. (2017, 1 2). Digital Games and Employment: Recommendations for Turkey. Journal of Entrepreneurship Innovation and Marketing Research, (pp. 136-153).
- Akdemir, B. (2017). The Changing Role of Human Resources Management in the Global Competition Environment: Beta Publishing, (pp. 266-173).
- Akgeyik, T. (2002). Strategic Human Resources Management,. Istanbul University Faculty of Economics Finance Research Center Conferences, (pp. 21-57).
- Aktan, Ç. C., & Şen, H. (1999). Globalization, Economic Crisis and Turkey. Ankara: TOSYÖV Publications, (pp. 243-248)

- Anonymous. (2024). Definition of a Great Workplace. Great Place To Work Organization Türkiye Representative Retrieved from <https://www.greatplacetowork.com.tr/hakkimizda/misyonumuz/>
- Anonymous. (2024). About the Certification Program. <https://www.greatplacetowork.com.tr>: Retrieved from <https://www.greatplacetowork.com.tr/certification>
- Bakraktaroğlu, S. (2002). Strategic and Non-Strategic Human Resources Management. Istanbul: Beta A.Ş, (pp.65-69).
- Capital. (2021). Capital Magazine Electronic Bulletin: Retrieved from <https://www.capital.com.tr/haberler>
- Das Gupta, A. (2020). Strategic Human Resource Management. Productivity Press, (pp 473-486).
- Düzgün, A., & Çetin, C. (2017). The Mediating Effect of Competitive Strategies on the Relationship Between Strategic Human Resources Management and Organizational Performance. International Journal of Management Economics and Business, (pp. 498-511).
- Guevara, P. (2024). A Quick Guide to 360 Degree Evaluation. Safeti Culture, (pp. 4-8).
- Malik, A. (2019). International Research Journal of Advanced Engineering and Science, (pp. 209-215).
- Malik, A. (2019). . Creating Competitive Advantage through Source Basic Capital Strategic Humanity in the Industrial Age 4.0. International Research Journal of Advanced Engineering and Science, (pp. 209-215).
- Manyika, J., Lund, S., Chui, M., Bughin, J., Woetzel, J., Batra, P., .Sanghvi, S. (2017). Jobs Lost, Jobs Gained: Workforce Transitions In A Time Of Automation. Mickensy Global Institute, (pp. 94-108).
- OECD. (2018). Gross domestic spending on R&D of countries. [www.oecd.org](http://stats.oecd.org/vie-whtml.aspx?datasetcode=MSTI_PUB&lang=en): Retrieved from http://stats.oecd.org/vie-whtml.aspx?datasetcode=MSTI_PUB&lang=en
- Örtenblad, A., Trehan, K., & Putnam, L. L. (2016). Exploring Morgan's Metaphors: Theory, Research, and Practice in Organizational Studies. SAGE Publications, Inc, (pp. 177-179).
- Purdy, L., & Coelho, A. (2003). Two Alternative Approaches to the Evaluation of Performance: 360-degree Feedback and the Balanced Scorecard. Harvard Business Review Publications, (pp. 257-260).
- Rosemary, B. (2002). Managing Customer Services: Human Resource Practices, Turnover, and Sales Growth. The Academy of Management Journal, (pp. 587-597).

Wikipedia. (2024,). Headhunting. Retrieved from Wikipedia https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Executive_search

Yaman, H., Çetin, D., & Dulupçu, MA (2020). R&D Expenditures and High Technology Exports in OECD Countries. *Anadolu University Journal of Social Sciences*, (pp. 193-208).

Yazıcı, Ö., & Gündüz, Y. (2011). Comparison of In-Service Training of Teachers in Some Developed Countries and Turkey. *Journal of Theoretical Education*, (pp. 1-15).

Yentür, DB (2023). *The Journey of Migration with the Brain*. Zet Academy Publications, (pp. 44-48).